

Chinese urban patient bed design for home care through the lens of culture, evolving care giving, architecture and home interiors

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Abstract:The growing elderly population in China, combined with elders' preference for home-based care, highlights the need to understand in situ caregiving practices. This study employs a secondary visual ethnography, analysing Chinese films and videos alongside scientific literature. Findings show that patient beds function as sites of filial piety, family bonding, and evolving caregiving practices, while also influencing furniture placement and spatial organization in urban homes. These insights inform new directions for culturally sensitive Chinese patient bed design. This study proposes a framework for technologically, culturally and spatially informed patient bed design not yet addressed in current Chinese literature.

Key Words: home based care giving, Chinese urban architecture and interiors, patient bed design, cultural techno spatial

Introduction:With growing elderly Chinese population, single child expected to display filial piety as a care giver and such caregivers themselves aging, patient beds have evolved beyond simple cranks and flaps into smartisation, yet most of the patient beds still operate on the same basic premise: the more the automation or smartisation the better it is expected to be. This supposedly predictable relationship seems to have overlooked other ethnographic factors at play in urban Chinese home based care giving. This is manifested as a gap in patient bed literature. This paper explores how urban Chinese home spaces, caregiving routines, and cultural expectations might inform patient bed design, identifying potential strategies to reconcile privacy, accessibility, and family engagement.

Literature Review:The literature survey includes:

- a. review of both regular academic texts such as journals and
- b. audio-visual sources such as magazines, iconic movies, promotional materials. These are under a separate sub-section labelled cultural-audio-visual media.

Part a)

1. Need for home-based care giving: Wang, Feng, et al [1] talks about design strategy for living space considering the imperative to age at home due to the gap between availability and affordability of caring homes.
2. Environmental preferences in Chinese homes by the elders- Muchun Li [2] talk about the preferences of urban elderly in terms of colours on walls, flooring, wall papers etc.
3. Community and professional support: Xiao, Feng et al [3] have looked at patterns of home care and community support and found distinct preferences among two classes for health

care professional visits. However, this has not looked into the type of home and bed requirement for the elderly with disabilities.

4. Filial Piety: Pan, Yquin et al [4] showed that the concept of filial piety is not only strong in the Chinese culture but probably needs to be encouraged as practicing it is stressful. It also showed that care giving is simultaneously a source of moral obligation as well as stress.
5. Comparative household structures: The book Elder Care Issues in China and India [5] describes India’s multi-generational households vs China’s nuclearized families.
6. Labour vs Love, the evolving care giving practices: Wu Xinyue’s study [6] talks about the current generation’s division of care giving in which they outsource the hard work of care giving to paid care givers and show filial piety by controlling the quality of care giving thru paid care givers and thru spending quality time with the patient. They spend this time even if the patient is in a care home.

Gap identified: There is no comprehensive research integrating **patient bed design, compact urban architecture, caregiver ergonomics, and filial piety** in Chinese home-based care.

The next part of the survey uses the above thread to explore the care giving through the ethnographic lens of audio visual and other local media rather than relying on purely academic researchers.

Part b)

Observations from Chinese AV media in the following OUTSIDE-IN-ORDER.

Architectural feature	Media Source	Details of the media source	Observation
Narrow single front doors	Sixth tone, “For Shanghai’s Dr House, every patient is a neighbour”	pic 8c	A typical urban, flat has a single narrow door
	Sixth tone, “For Shanghai’s Dr House, every patient is a neighbour”	pic 8i	
Narrow staircase	Sixth tone, “For Shanghai’s Dr House, every patient is a	pic 8b	The building staircase is narrow

	neighbour”		
	Sixth tone, “For Shanghai’s Dr House, every patient is a neighbour”	pic 8m	
No elevators	Sixth tone, “For Shanghai’s Dr House, every patient is a neighbour”	pic 8k	No elevator to go to the flats. climb up the stairs

House Interior and spatial arrangement	Media Source	Details of the media source	Observation
Urban residential flats are small and narrow	YouTube video of CNA Insider titled “China’s nursing home stigma: Who will care for the elderly”	pic 7e	Residential flats are likely to be small and rectangular
	Sixth tone, “For Shanghai’s Dr House, every patient is a neighbour”	pic 8e	The room is small, the bed narrow, a single middle-aged care giver present
Space needed around the bed for patient accessibility by other service care givers and health care professionals	Sixth Tone “In Shanghai, a Splash of Comfort in Elderly Care: Home Bathing Services.” Published in Dec 2023,	pics 9a and 9b	An elderly bed ridden patient being bathed and cared for. The room seems comparatively cluttered. The bed in the pic is a patient bed
Bed location to offer maximum possible privacy for the patient, elderly	YouTube video of CNA Insider titled “China’s nursing home stigma: Who will care for the elderly”	pic 7c,7d	Inside rooms are reserved for the privacy of the urban elderly
	Sixth tone, “For Shanghai’s Dr House, every patient is a neighbour”	pic 8g	The bed is in a corner of the room for probably maximum possible privacy under the circumstances, such that the patient is not seen from the flat entrance
	Sixth tone, “For Shanghai’s Dr House, every patient is a neighbour”	pic 8d	The patient is in the room one enters but to the side
Disorganization and	Sixth tone, “For	pic 8a	The elderly bed ridden person is

clutter on and around the bed	Shanghai's Dr House, every patient is a neighbour"		in a very small, cluttered room
	Sixth tone, "For Shanghai's Dr House, every patient is a neighbour"	pic 8f	The patient is on a regular bed, the bed seems cluttered
	Sixth tone, "For Shanghai's Dr House, every patient is a neighbour"	pic 8a, pic 8j	A small room with a regular and not a patient bed, the bed probably narrow and the room cluttered with possible medication bottles kept on the window ledges/ shelves.
New Tech for the bedridden patient	China's Elderly Embrace Big Tech, Senior-Friendly Products - People's Daily Online.	pic 10a	New Tech available for feeding an elderly bed ridden, probably disabled person, consuming bed side space and requiring accessibility

Care giver characteristics	Media Source	Details of the media source	Observation
Care giver, single person, not young-but a middle-aged person, family member	YouTube video of CNA Insider titled "China's nursing home stigma: Who will care for the elderly"	Pic 7a, pic 7b	Single female child supporting two elderly parents
	Sixth tone, "For Shanghai's Dr House, every patient is a neighbour"	pic 8h	The care giver is middle aged
	Sixth tone, "For Shanghai's Dr House, every patient is a neighbour"	pic 8l	An elderly couple probably on their own, with the bedridden elderly woman on a regular double bed
	Sixth Tone "In Shanghai, a Splash of Comfort in Elderly Care: Home Bathing Services." Published in Dec 2023,	pic 9c	An elderly daughter learning the apps to call for such baths by registering etc.
	2011 iconic Hong	pic 11a	Shows the filial duty

	Kong movie "A Simple Life",		being performed by a single man
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Discussions and design implications:

Patient beds in urban China sit at the intersection of culture, architectural patterns, interior (spatial) constraints, evolving care giving practices, care giver's demographics and their varying skills and upcoming technologies.

Paper 2: Smart Bed Sociotechnical Interface

Architectural constraints of compact urban flats, narrow doors, narrow staircases and absence of elevators demand a bed with light weight materials, modular components and narrow structure. A rollable structure will allow them to fit into corners enabling patient privacy and space for movement near the bed. Narrowness probably is the single most important requirement because it will free up space and allow access to patient for set up of –1) professional services such as bathing 2) “love” services such as the elder patient’s feet and hair washing by the family 3) sofas, couches near the bed for “affectionate visit-based family interactions” 4) newer robotic tech 5) access by doctors and health care professionals 6) storage facility near the patient bed for medicines and mattresses.

Varying care giving skills, mixed gender of and middle age of care givers, demanding minimum physical strength in caregiving requires patient beds to be automated to varying levels, be safe and ergonomic.

Conclusion:

Ultimately, the Chinese urban patient bed must function not only as medical equipment but as a **cultural and techno-spatial anchor**—balancing labor reduction, emotional connection, cultural norms, architectural -interior spatial adaptability and base for newer technologies.

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Pic 7a

Pic 7b

Pic 7c

Pic 7d

Pic 7e

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Pic 8a

Pic 8b

Pic 8c

Pic 8d

Pic 8e

Pic 8f

Pic 8g

Pic 8h

Pic 8i

Pic 8j

Pic 8k

Pic 8l

Pic 8m

MULTIMEDIA

For Shanghai's Dr. House, Every Patient Is a Neighbor

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Pic 9a

Pic 9b

Pic 9c

10) China's Elderly Embrace Big Tech, Senior-Friendly Products - People's Daily Online.
<https://en.people.cn/n3/2021/0715/c90000-9872409.html>.

Pic 10a

A patient eats by mind-controlling the robotic arm in the Second Affiliated Hospital of Zhejiang University School of Medicine in Hangzhou, east China's Zhejiang Province, Jan. 9, 2020. (Photo/Xinhua)

11) - YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aQPoGH5e5Pg> (A Simple Life)

Pic 11a

